

Dynamical Analysis of Beams Lying on Discontinuous Linear Winkler Foundation

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Abstract

Analysing the dynamic behavior of beams lying on a discontinuous linear Winkler foundation involves considering the interaction between the beam and the supporting foundation. The Winkler foundation is a simplified model that represents the soil or support underneath the beam as a series of linear springs. When the foundation is discontinuous, it means that the properties of the foundation change along the length of the beam. The geometry of the beam, including length, cross-sectional shape, and material properties is defined while obtaining the mathematical model.

The discontinuous linear Winkler foundation is established by specifying the spring constants or stiffness values along the length of the beam. The discontinuity could occur at certain points or intervals. The equation of motion involves considering the forces and moments acting on the beam, including the effects of the foundation springs. For solving the dynamic equations, numerical methods or analytical solutions based on mode shapes and frequencies are used. To understand how the dynamic response is influenced by the interaction between the beam and the discontinuous linear Winkler foundation, dynamic amplification factors are evaluated.

Keywords: Linear Winkler foundation, dynamical analysis, discontinuous beam

Introduction

A beam resting on a discontinuous linear Winkler foundation refers to a beam situated on a Winkler foundation with varying stiffness or support conditions at specific points or regions. This situation frequently occurs in real-world applications where the soil or foundation conditions are not homogeneous. The Winkler foundation is modeled as a series of independent, linear elastic springs instead of a continuous soil. In this model, each unit (spring) of the soil responds only to the displacements directly beneath it. A beam is a horizontal structural element that carries loads over a certain length and resists bending and shear forces. Discontinuity means sudden changes in stiffness or foundation conditions. A beam resting on a discontinuous linear Winkler foundation can be defined as a structure where the foundation stiffness, k , varies along its length. This situation may involve regions of different stiffness or sudden changes at specific points.

Examples of this type of systems are beams resting on different types of soil (for example, one part on sandy soil, the other part on clay soil), beams with foundation reinforcement in certain regions and beams remaining on natural soil in other regions, and structural elements resting on soil layers with different stiffnesses. Beams lying on discontinuous linear Winkler foundations are structural systems that are frequently encountered in real-world applications with varying foundation conditions and need to be analyzed carefully. Analysis of such structures is important to understand the effects of changes in foundation stiffness on the bending and vibration behavior of the beam.

Beams lying on discontinuous linear Winkler foundations are used in cases where soil and foundation conditions are heterogeneous, encountered in various engineering and construction projects. Such beams help optimize the stability and performance of structures by sitting on soils of different stiffnesses or improved soil regions. These applications span a wide range of areas, such as bridges, buildings, industrial structures, roads, marine structures, soil improvement projects and water/energy substructure projects.

There are various studies on the subject in the literature. Daniel [1] present a detailed investigation of the vibration analysis of beams on a linear Winkler elastic foundation using the differential transform method. Dönmez Demir et.al. [2] consider the behavior of beams modeled a linear spring foundation with a discontinuous function. Karasin and Alitas [3] introduce computationally manageable finite grid solution of plates as an application of finite element method for a beam element on a Winkler foundation. Boral et. al. [4] analyse the time-dependent motion of flexural waves generated by the vibration of an elastic plate resting on a variable Winkler foundation with compression.

This study focuses on the dynamical analysis of beams resting on discontinuous linear Winkler foundations. In cases where foundation stiffness differs in certain regions, the beam can be analyzed using piecewise differential equations. Separate equations are written for each region and the solution is made by considering the boundary conditions and transition conditions.

Equation of Motion

The equation of motion of a beam supported a Winkler foundation with two-span characterizes its dynamic behavior, integrating geometric properties, material characteristics, and interaction with the foundation. Generally, this equation is introduced as [5]

$$\tilde{E}\tilde{I}\tilde{w}_i^{iv} + \tilde{P}\tilde{w}_i'' + \tilde{k}(x)\tilde{w}_i + \rho\tilde{A}\ddot{\tilde{w}}_i = 0 \tag{1}$$

where \tilde{w} denotes displacement. \tilde{E} , \tilde{I} , \tilde{P} is modulus of elasticity, moment of inertia, axial load, respectively. \tilde{k} represents spring coefficient. \tilde{A} denotes cross-sectional area and ρ is defined by density of material. The notation (\prime) indicates a derivative with respect to the spatial, x along the beam and $(\dot{})$ represents a derivative with respect to time t . Then, the beam with two span is considered as two separate regions as follows;

Figure 1. A two-span beam resting on a Winkler foundation

I. Region: $\tilde{E}\tilde{I}\tilde{w}_1^{iv} + \tilde{P}\tilde{w}_1'' + \tilde{k}_1(x)\tilde{w}_1 + \tilde{\rho}\tilde{A}\ddot{\tilde{w}}_1 = 0 \tag{2}$

II. Region: $\tilde{E}\tilde{I}\tilde{w}_2^{iv} + \tilde{P}\tilde{w}_2'' + \tilde{\rho}\tilde{A}\ddot{\tilde{w}}_2 = 0 \tag{3}$

To get rid of shape and material dependency, the nondimensionalization process is performed on Eq. (1)

$$w_i^{iv} + P w_i'' + k_i w_i + \dot{w}_i = 0 \tag{4}$$

where the dimensionless terms are

$$w = \frac{\tilde{w}}{r^2}, \quad t = \frac{\tilde{t}}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{E}\tilde{I}}{\rho\tilde{A}}}, \quad x = \frac{\tilde{x}}{L}, \quad r = \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{I}}{\tilde{A}}}, \quad P = \frac{\tilde{P}}{L^2} \tag{5}$$

For two separate regions, the dimensionless beam equation becomes

$$w_1^{iv} + P w_1'' + k w_1 + \dot{w}_1 = 0 \tag{6}$$

$$w_2^{iv} + P w_2'' + \dot{w}_2 = 0 \tag{7}$$

where the spring coefficient are considered as $k_1 = k$ and $k_2 = 0$ for the two regions. The displacement and moment are zero at the fixed support, thus the boundary conditions are given by

$$\begin{aligned} w_1(0, t) &= 0 \\ w_2(1, t) &= 0 \\ w_1''(0, t) &= 0 \\ w_2''(1, t) &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

In the transition region, displacement, rotation, moment and shear forces are also equal. Then, the transition conditions are as follows;

$$w_1(x_1, t) = w_2(x_1, t)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 w_1'(x_1, t) &= w_2'(x_1, t) & (9) \\
 w_1''(x_1, t) &= w_2''(x_1, t) \\
 w_1'''(x_1, t) + P w_1'(x_1, t) &= w_2'''(x_1, t) + P w_2'(x_1, t)
 \end{aligned}$$

Solutions

The linear equations obtained for the first and second regions are analytically solved. Substituting the proposed solutions

$$w_1(x) = X_1(x). e^{i\omega_n t} \tag{10}$$

$$w_2(x) = X_2(x). e^{i\omega_n t} \tag{11}$$

into Eqs. (6) and (7), respectively, the resulting equations are obtained as follows;

$$X_1^{iv}(x) + P X_1''(x) + k X_1(x) - \omega_n^2 X_1(x) = 0 \tag{12}$$

$$X_2^{iv}(x) + P X_2''(x) - \omega_n^2 X_2(x) = 0 \tag{13}$$

where boundary conditions are reformulated as

$$X_1(0) = 0, X_2(1) = 0, X_1''(0) = 0, X_2''(1) = 0 \tag{14}$$

and transient conditions are

$$X_1(x_1) = X_2(x_1); X_1'(x_1) = X_2'(x_1) \tag{15}$$

$$X_1''(x_1) = X_2''(x_1)$$

$$X_1'''(x_1) + P X_1'(x_1) = X_2'''(x_1) + P X_2'(x_1)$$

The solution of differential equation (12) is in the form

$$X_1(x) = c. e^{rx} \tag{16}$$

Substituting the solution (16) into Eq. (12) yields

$$r^4 + P r^2 - \omega_n^2 + k = 0 \tag{17}$$

If the obtained 4th-degree polynomial is solved, then roots of the characteristic equation are found as

$$r_{1,2,3,4} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{\pm 2\sqrt{P^2 + 4\omega_n^2 - 4k} - 2P}}{2} \tag{18}$$

Substituting the roots of Eq. (17) into equation (16), one obtains

$$X_1(x) = c_1 e^{r_1 x} + c_2 e^{r_2 x} + c_3 e^{r_3 x} + c_4 e^{r_4 x} \tag{19}$$

Similarly, the solution of Eq. (13) in the 2nd region is proposed as

$$X_2(x) = a. e^{sx} \tag{20}$$

where the roots of the characteristic equation are

$$s_{1,2,3,4} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{\pm 2\sqrt{P^2 + 4\omega_n^2} - 2P}}{2} \tag{21}$$

Then, the solution is obtained as

$$X_2(x) = a_1 e^{s_1 x} + a_2 e^{s_2 x} + a_3 e^{s_3 x} + a_4 e^{s_4 x} \tag{22}$$

Numerical Results

Table 1. Variation of critical value of *P* for various values, *k* ($\omega_n = 0$)

x_1	0.3	0.5	0.7
<i>k</i> = 100	9.949874371	11.24158422	12.74291610
<i>k</i> = 500	11.93991934	17.20157131	22.33830790
<i>k</i> = 1000	13.86047486	21.38771759	31.62277660

Table 2. Variation of natural frequencies, ω_n for various values, k ($P = 0$)

x_1	0.3	0.5	0.7
$k = 100$	10.57731269	12.08985164	13.49582897
$k = 500$	12.75242331	17.80062165	22.62967836
$k = 1000$	14.59153265	21.94015433	31.62277660

Table 3. Variation of natural frequencies, ω_n for different values, k ($P = 2$)

x_1	0.3	0.5	0.7
$k = 100$	9.949874371	11.24158422	12.74291610
$k = 500$	11.93991934	17.20157131	22.33830790
$k = 1000$	13.86047486	21.38771759	31.62277660

Table 4. Variation of natural frequencies, ω_n for different values, k ($P = 5$)

x_1	0.3	0.5	0.7
$k = 100$	7.905145463	9.682458366	11.52154421
$k = 500$	10.60283733	16.25571355	22.36067977
$k = 1000$	12.67965549	20.51763227	31.52380053

Table 5. Variation of natural frequencies, ω_n for different values, k ($P = 10$)

x_1	0.3	0.5	0.7
$k = 100$	3.618491188	6.866976479	9.129279831
$k = 500$	7.875862272	14.52138965	21.79449472
$k = 1000$	10.39707586	18.93299941	31.22498999

Conclusion

The critical axial load, which is the minimum load value that causes the beam to buckle, is calculated to obtain numerical results. Natural frequency values at different axial load values are compared. It has been observed that as the length of the first span increases, the natural frequency also increases. As a result, it has been seen that as the critical load value increases, the natural frequency decreases.

As the critical load increases, the risk of buckling of the structural member increases. Factors that increase the critical load also increase the stiffness of the element. As stiffness increases, natural frequency generally increases. However, when the critical load increases, especially when axial pressure forces affect to the structure, natural frequencies may decrease. More clearly, the axial compressive force reduces the effective stiffness of the structure, which causes the natural frequencies to decrease. That is, as the axial pressure forces on the element increase (approaching the critical load), the dynamic behavior of the element is affected and its natural frequencies decrease. The decrease in natural frequency as the critical load value increases is due to the fact that axial loads reduce the rigidity of the structural element and, as a result, the vibration properties change. This relationship is an important factor to be considered in the design and analysis of structures. This connection between the stability and dynamic behavior of structures is of critical importance, especially for elongated elements at risk of buckling.

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